

Literature review of *Bhela Samhita* related to *Shalakyta tantra*

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Abstract

Shalakyta Tantra is one among the *ashtanga* of *Ayurveda*. it is also called *Urdhvanga*. Understanding of *Shalakyta Tantra* will help the physician in the planning of treatments for the diseases related to *urdhvanga*. *Sushruta Samhita* is considered as the main text for the *shalakyta* references. There are many other treatises which are having hidden *chikitsa* principles related to *shalakyta* diseases. one such text is *bhela Samhita* written by *acharya bhela*. *Acharya bhela* explained *nidana*, *Lakshana*, and *chikitsa* of various *shalakyta* tantra-related diseases. Unfortunately, 50% part of *shiroga roga chikitsa adhyaya* is not available. So, it is an attempt to analyze and explore the remaining part for finding out new hidden treatment principles.

Keywords: *Bhela Samhita*; *Shalakyta*; *Ayurveda*; *Shiro roga*; *Chikitsa*

1. Introduction

Acharya bhela was one among six disciples of *atreya punarvasu*. He wrote a treatise named *bhela Samhita*. It comprises 120 chapters divided into 8 *sthana*. As per the point of view of *shalakyta tantra* chapter no 21- *Shiro roga chikitsa* is of much importance. This chapter contains *nidana*, *Lakshana*, and *chikitsa* of *shiro rogas karna roga*, *mukha roga* & *arochaka* like *suryavarta*, *anantavata*, *Shira Kampa*, *krimija karna roga*. 50% part of this chapter is missing. So, this study is done by keeping in mind to enlighten the knowledge of the importance of the remaining part related to the *shalakyta tantra* in *bhela Samhita*. This study will review the hidden knowledge of various *chikitsa* principles & help in better understanding of diseases related to *shalakyta tantra* in *bhela Samhita*.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Chapter No.21- Shiro Roga Chikitsa

Starting part and last part of this chapter are missing. Available contents regarding *chikitsa* are reviewed in this study

2.1.1. shankhak chikitsa (1)

Application and pouring of cold *kashaya* of *dravyas* should be done repeatedly.

2.1.2. suryavarta (2)

- intake of *kalyanaka ghrita* should be done
- both *Vamana* and *shirovirechana* should be performed.

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- after snehana, Nasya karma should be done.
- Shirobasti procedure with ghrita, taila, and vasa should be done.
- Nasya prepared by mamsa of Mayura, kukkuta processed with butter and jeevaniya drugs helps in relieving from suryavarta.
- Parisechana should be done overhead by ksheera Siddha Kashaya prepared from dravyas like bilwa, amsumati, rasna, sahdeva, punarnava, guducchi, Bala, yasthimadhu, etc.
- Poultice made by jangala mamsa is beneficial in daruna suryavarta.

2.1.3. *anantavata (3)*

- acharya bhela told special nidana like palalam, dadhi, matsya, pistha anna sevana & divaswapana for the manifestation of anantavata vyadhi
- Chikitsa- siravyadhana of lalata Pradesh sira
- Snehapana followed by virechana should be done.
- Suryavarta treatment principles should be followed.

2.1.4. *ardhavbhedaka (4)*

- Chikitsa- shirovirechana, nasya
- Maximum dose of taila or ghrita or vasa should be given to patient for the purpose of Snehana and pacification of disease.
- Nadi swedana should be done.
- Upnaha sweda should be done to head by using ushna ksheer siddha drugs.

2.1.5. *Nasyadi karma in shiroroga (5)*

- In all type of shiro roga shiroverchana with done by using drugs like -karanja, shigru, twak, patra, sharkara.
- Dahana karma should be done in shiras and lalata Pradesh last part & manya Pradesh by using pippali kanda.
- If there is severe pain in vatajanya shiro roga & kaphaja shiroroga then wise physician should done dahana karma by using aarandya pippali kanda.

2.1.6. *shira kampa (6)*

- *Nidana*- persons who consumes daily dry food & those are suffering from *udavarta*
- *Chikitsa*- mild sudation, internal intake of *bala taila* should be done
- Daily *nasya karma, anuvasana, snehapana* should be done.

2.1.7. *murdha kshvyathu (7)*

- *Nidana*- intake of Sarva rasa yukta bhojana in case of ajirna & doing adhyashana.
- *Chikitsa*- sira vyadhana of shiras sira.
- Purana ghrita pana
- Shodhana dhoomapana
- Shirovirechana

2.1.8. *Kantha roga chikitsa (8)*

- use of *Bala taila* is ideal for both *nasya* and oral intake.
- If *Kantha roga* is due to both *Vata & Kapha dosha*, then *Kavala* should be done by using *Kalka* or *Kashaya* in *Mukha* and *Kantha*.

2.1.9. *arochaka chikitsa (9)*

- Powder of drugs like pippali, pippalimoola, maricha, haritaki, shunthi, yavakshara, lodhra, and tejovati should be mixed with honey.
- Face should be washed by using the above-said drugs.
- Withholding of powders of drugs like adraka, kapittha, trikatu along with madhu & sharkara in the mouth is said as the best in all types of arochaka.

- Kavala by using dravyas like jeeraka, maricha, draksha, chincha, dadima, souvarchala lavana mixed with jaggery and honey is said as best in arochaka

2.1.10. galasundika chikitsa (10)

- Chikitsa- siravyadhana, snehapana & shirovirechana should be done by using teekshna dravyas
- Shastra karma & dumapana can be done

2.1.11. Karna roga (11)

- Dosh predominance -karna shola- vatajanya, karna vata- vata, badhirya – vata & kapha

2.1.12. Karna roga chikitsa

- Snehapana, nasya, nadi sweda, poultice (upnaha). And karnapoorana by using vasa and majja of anoopa Pradesh animals.
- Bilwadi taila karnapoorana is said to be best for any type of daruna karnashoola
- A mixture of shaireesh taila & shatpaka taila & Bala taila karnapoorana is beneficial in severe earache & badhirya.

2.1.13. Raktaja Karna roga (12)

- *Lakshana*- swelling, pain & redness
- *Chikitsa*- *siravyadhana* of *lalata sira*, *virechana karma*, *shiro virechana* & cotton dipped with *amla dravya* processed oil should be placed over the head.
- In case of the suppurative stage- poultice should be applied over wound & apply *Vrana taila* overwound
- If pus is coming- take a Probe and apply cotton over the head of it and clean the discharge slowly
- After cleaning *karnapoorana* should be done for 1 *muhurta* by using oil prepared by drugs like *sunthi*, *maricha*, *pippali*, *saindhava lavana*, *majishtha*, *rasna*, *haridra*, *tilvaka*, *tila*, *asana*, *eranda*, *moorva*, *arka*, etc along with *mamsa* of mangoos & donkey and skin of snake, etc .this will help in reducing the *karnasrava*, *karnashoola*, *karnapaka*, *badhirya* and also *Shiro rogas*.

2.1.14. Krimija karna roga (13)

- *lakshana*- severe pain forehead along with burning sensation in the head, pricking type of pain, giddiness etc. all symptoms are similar to symptoms of *krimija Shiro roga*.
- If more than one symptom is present then the prognosis is considered to be very bad.
- *chikitsa*- *Madhu shukta* or milk or *sura* should be made lukewarm and *karnapoorana* should be done and the head should be made straight. if the discharge occurs after the removal of the insect, then the line of treatment of *karna srava* should be followed.

3. Conclusion

There are many other Samhitas in that knowledge related to *shalakya tantra* is extinct because of various factors or still not reviewed. Scholars mainly refer *bruhat trayais* for *shalakya* diseases treatment. So, this study will help scholars for getting added information on *shalakya tantra* written in *bhela Samhita* and also it will helpful for further research over *chikitsa* principles explained in *bhela Samhita*.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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